

Nurses as patients during the COVID-19 pandemic: Traversing caring encounters

Christian S. Tu ■ Marinette J. Dupaya ■ Rosell P. Gutierrez ■ Evelyn F. Tadena ■ Marvin M. Dispolo ■
 Oliver A. Virata ■ Eric Jacildo ■ Gemma Tapawan ■ Laarleen Pamaran ■ Rychel Casing

Abstract

This study aims to explore the roles and responsibilities of Nurses during the COVID-19 pandemic and how they managed to take care of other people after their own recovery from COVID-19 infection. The purpose of this research is to explore the lived experiences of nurses as patients during the COVID-19 pandemic and navigate caring encounters. The study was conducted in St. Dominic Medical Center. The researchers utilized phenomenological design. Online distribution and collection of data were conducted among four nurses who were purposively selected from November 2020 to January 2021. Data responses were submitted online by the participants and validated by the researchers. The thematic approach was employed all through out the data analysis. Six themes were developed based on the responses of the participants, including 'fear of losing myself,' 'anxiety is contagious,' 'feeling betrayed by the government,' 'being rejected,' 'very supportive of our needs,' and 'I miss my family.' Results of the study were utilized by the nurses, other frontliners and the general population in battling or combating COVID-19.

Keywords: Nurses. Patients. Covid-19 Pandemic. Caring encounters.

Christian S. Tu*

St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines
 ctu@sdca.edu.ph

Marinette J. Dupaya

St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines
 mdupaya@sdca.edu.ph

Rosell P. Gutierrez

St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines
 rpgutierrez@sdca.edu.ph

Evelyn F. Tadena

St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines
 evelyn_tadena@sdca.edu.ph

Marvin M. Dispolo

St. Dominic College of Asia, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines
 mdispolo@sdca.edu.ph

Oliver A. Virata

Eric Jacildo

Gemma Tapawan

Laarleen Pamaran

Rychel Casing

St. Dominic Medical Center, Bacoor, Cavite, Philippines

*Corresponding author

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has taught all of humanity a valuable lesson. It is a major setback for the global healthcare system as well as the educational sector. COVID-19 is linked to a high rate of infection and toll-death, which has resulted in a high level of fear and worry about becoming infected, affecting people's sanity. As a result of the pandemic, human freedom of movement has been severely restricted, and all countries around the world have been placed under lockdown. The body of literature about laboratory testing, preventive measures, and management guidelines for dealing with the highly infectious virus is consistently expanding. The statistics on mental health difficulties among front-line warriors and health-care personnel is well-documented as well. All are treated equally rich or poor due to the risk of acquiring the disease.

On December 31, 2019, the WHO Country Office in China received the first report of Coronavirus Disease 2019 (COVID-19), which was discovered in Wuhan, China. It spread to 218 countries and territories around the world, as well as two international modes of travel (Worldometers, 2020). As of April 17, 2021, there are 219 countries are affected by COVID-19 and in total the number of cases are 140,547,010 confirmed cases around the globe. This includes 3,012,658 deaths and 119,371,496 recovered from debilitating disease (WHO, 2021). In the Philippines with about 926,052 total number of active cases, it includes 15,810 confirmed deaths and 706,532 recovered from COVID-19 (DOH, 2021).

The biggest challenge in the Philippines is the excessive number of COVID-19 cases and the health care systems of the country suffered due to lack of resources to fight against the virus. Lack of hospital facilities and insufficient number of nurses are the greatest challenges among Filipino nurses. Being overworked underpaid is a challenge of our front liners which complicates a lot of stress to everyone. Due to the quickly shifting scenario, a lack of specialist understanding of the evolving unique disease, and the constant additional information that is made available locally and worldwide as it is discovered, leaders are faced with complexity, ambiguity, and uncertainty in strategic planning (Djalante et al., 2020; Gunawan, et al., 2021).

The WHO had chosen 2020 as the year of the nurse long before the COVID-19 epidemic. Nurses are the major heroes in the fight against COVID-19, as they play critical roles in the virus's testing, treatment, and containment (Visagie, 2020). Nurses are on the front lines of the epidemic response, sacrificing their lives to care for others. COVID-19 has claimed the lives of 1,500 nurses in 44 nations as of October 28, 2020 (ICN, 2020). In addition to the report from the International Council of Nurses there are about 471 infected by the novel virus (ICN, 2021). Nurses' contributions are invaluable around the world and in the Philippines, and the response to COVID-19 would not be possible without the critical role nurses play in its treatment and containment.

Given the critical role of nurses in the fight against COVID-19, the goal of this study was to explore about their lived experiences of nurses at St. Dominic Medical Center as the main frontliners in traversing the caring counters as being the patient with COVID-19 virus. Basically, this study would provide crucial information needed optimally to support and recognized the effort of Nursing Service Office of St. Dominic Medical Center.

COVID-19 as a Public Health Crisis in the Philippines

The COVID-19 pandemic is intensifying the Philippines' long-standing problems with an unstable and inequitable public health system. The country has become an epidemic calamity waiting to happen due to its highly packed capital, significant social inequities, and inadequate infrastructure (Naguit, 2020).

With its comparatively ill-equipped health system, the Philippines, like any other country whose health system has been put to the test, is expected to be overwhelmed by the rise of COVID-19 cases. In a country with a population of 100 million people, a lack of hospital beds in both normal and critical care, as well as mechanical ventilators and masks, are among the most pressing challenges.

Days after the lockdown was announced, it became clear that action plans and centralized control would not be sufficient to secure social safety for all Filipinos. It was a battle cry for civil society organizations to take a more active role in combating the pandemic. Without wishing to romanticize the concept of resilience, Filipinos have long been renowned to persevere in the face of the country's frequent environmental and humanitarian catastrophes. This pandemic is not really any different. Decentralized agreements between firms and workers have been created to assist mitigate the damage. Some companies are paying employees on a regular basis and implementing flexible work schedules, while others are directly providing cash help to employees. Short-term measures that are less optimum but provide immediate relief but are not guaranteed to assist workers in the long run include releasing workers' thirteenth month salary and utilizing leave credits during the quarantine period.

Innovation and resourcefulness

Improvising local initiatives and creative innovations are the call for the day in the face of the quickly expanding COVID-19 issue. They are crucial in addressing the shortages of personal protective equipment (PPE), testing kits, and critical infrastructure. The National Institute of Health (NIH) created a local antigen-based screening test kit that reduced the cost and time it took to get results. Models for hygienic tents were developed by University of the Philippines students, which were used by local government units. Due to a shortage of PPE, garment workers joined with infectious disease specialists to create a mask design and temporarily convert their workplace into a temporary mask production. Village populations began constructing face shields out of commonplace materials (Naguit, 2020).

Social reorganization as a source of solidarity

It is indeed incredibly encouraging to see how many social solidarity breakthroughs are arising, which are just as vital as technological discoveries. Schools, hotels, and event venues have opened their doors to people with minor COVID-19 symptoms. Cafes and dorms have opened to house front-line workers and homeless individuals. Various individuals have initiated fundraising campaigns for marginalized groups, created databases to match donations with persons in need, and assisted in government relief efforts. Free online consultations are also being offered by professionals in several disciplines via social media sites (Naguit, 2020).

Underpaid, overworked front-line workers facing stigma and discrimination

While most people react to the pandemic with a strong sense of community, popular fear of the virus's spread has resulted in discriminatory acts against front-line workers. Some front-liners have been ejected from their boarding house, denied access to food, and have been subjected to violence as a result of their vulnerability to the illness. Five men sprayed a corrosive disinfectant on a nurse in the southern Philippines. After being accused of carrying COVID-19-positive patients, an ambulance driver in Quezon City was shot in the hand. Health care employees valiantly continue to work despite the risk to their personal or family's health and reduced compensation (Naguit, 2020)

Public health crisis about social justice

Even in normal times, comprehensive health care is excessively expensive and out of reach for many Filipinos. Filipinos pay for more than half of their entire health-care costs themselves. Every year, an estimated one million people are pushed into poverty due to medical bills. In the Philippines, six out of ten individuals die without seeing a doctor. Any public health crisis stems from a lack of social fairness. In the Philippines, civil society has taken up much of the burden, undertaking responsibilities that the government must promptly address, such as raising funds for more PPE and tests, assuring the welfare of front-line workers, and ensuring food availability and distribution. The government's response to this situation has failed to fill a significant gap. Hands-on civil society projects based on solidarity and fairness remain a source of optimism at this crucial moment in history (Naguit, 2020).

Problem Statement

The study aims to explore the lived experience of SDMC Nurses as patients during the COVID-19 pandemic and to traverse caring encounters. The participants answered the following qualitative questions:

1. What is the lived experience of nurses as patients with COVID-19?
2. How did the SDMC nurses traverse their experience as COVID-19 patients?
3. What themes can further illuminate within the purview of Nursing as Caring Inquiry?
4. What realizations did SDMC Nurses develop after having survived COVID-19?

Methods

Research Design

The researchers used a phenomenological design based from Van Manen's phenomenology of practice (Van Manen, 2014) to explore lived experiences of SDMC Nurses as being the patient during COVID-19 pandemic and to traverse caring encounters. Hermeneutic phenomenology is a philosophical and human science method for exploring phenomena through lived experience (Polit & Beck, 2013). When it comes to human settings of practice, phenomenology is inherently practical, especially in nursing as it relates to the human sciences, because they always present unique situations (Van Manen, 2014). Phenomenology is a unique philosophy that aids us in responding competently and adaptively to each individual in each time, place, and circumstance (Van Manen, 2014).

Phenomenological themes are used to characterize the phenomenon (Van Manen, 2014). Interpreting the meaning of a lived experience depicted in the phenomenological text as approachable in terms of meaning units, structures of meaning, or themes is referred to as thematic knowledge (Van Manen, 2014). Basically, a theme is a conceptual formulation that has phenomenological force for the development of its description and is based on the categorical statement of the participants.

Research Sample and Setting

It is assumed that nurses are experiencing working under stressful conditions especially during pandemic. Sharing of interview questions in an online basis strategy to support them and understand their situation about how they live their lives every day. Therefore, it is easy for them to participate in this study voluntarily. The respondents are two female nurses and two males who were assigned in different clinical areas in St. Dominic Medical Center.

The inclusion criteria in this study are registered nurses with confirmed cases of COVID-19 who tested positive using RT-PCR swab test and admitted in St. Dominic Medical Center or home quarantine.

Data Collection

This study was conducted from November 2020 to January 2021 at St. Dominic Medical Center in Bacoor City, Cavite. This city has the greatest number of COVID19 cases in Cavite (DOHR4). Data were collected after the approval of the topic and research permission from hospital had been obtained. The Nursing Service Office especially head nurses and supervisors facilitated the research to contact the participants by providing their names and phone numbers. Some participants were approached through Facebook messenger and head nurses made constant follow-up of their availability of interview schedule.

The semi-structured online interview and video calls were conducted in our own dialect. The reason why the researchers utilized an online interview was because face-to-face interview was not allowed for the health & safety of the interviewer. The main investigators performed the interview, which lasted 30-60 minutes and included chatting whenever the researchers had a question based on the participants' responses.

In addition, the participants were given a set of questions on paper that they may answer on their own. After three days, the papers were returned. In consideration to their busy work, the participants were given enough time to write their experiences on paper. Before data collection, the researchers designed and prepared the interview guidelines.

Interview Questions

1. How do you feel today?
2. Are you still afraid, worried, stressed and depressed from your previous diagnosis of (COVID-19)?
3. Could you describe how you dealt with your life when you were diagnosed with COVID-19?
4. How many hours was your shift during pre-pandemic? Do you think it is one of the contributing factors to your diagnosis?
5. Could you describe how other people treated you before and after having COVID-19?
6. Did the hospital support you with what you needed when you were diagnosed with COVID-19? Could you please tell us what kind of support they gave?
7. Could you tell us how you felt when you saw the result as positive to COVID-19?
8. How did people react towards you when they heard you are a positive to COVID-19? Could you describe it?

However, until the researchers reached data saturation or when the researchers read the same remarks repeatedly, more questions were asked depending on the participants' responses. This study did not include a written interview; instead, only chats were conducted for clarification. Each interview and transcript was collectively studied, reviewed, and discussed by all researchers.

Data Analysis

The researchers used Van Manen's approach (Van Manen, 2015) in this study, which included: (1) turning the nature of lived experience by formulating the research question of this study ('what is the lived experience of nurses in the battle of COVID-19?'), (2) investigating the experience of the participants through semi-structured interviews and chats, (3) reflecting on the key themes through careful reading and listening of all interview transcripts, (4) re-reading the initial themes and constantly revising and refining thought; (5) maintaining a strong and oriented relationship to the phenomenon by reflecting back to the themes based on their written responses; and (6) maintaining a strong and oriented relationship to the phenomenon by reflecting back to the themes based on their written responses. All of these findings were transcribed into English from Filipino.

Ethical Considerations

The study approval was obtained after the proposal by the Research and Development Office of St. Dominic College of Asia. Prior to data collection, the researchers ensured that all participants had signed the written informed consent and understood the goal and processes of this study. The proponents of this study were verified and confirmed for each of participants through a written consent. The researchers treated all the data with utmost confidentiality and ensured that all information will be published anonymously.

Trustworthiness

To assure the research's credibility, it was peer-reviewed by qualified researchers and phenomenologists to ensure that there was no bias in the analysis and development of the themes. To assure dependability, methodological difficulties were addressed. The outcomes of the research study were also forwarded to the participants for clarification and validation of their responses, which was done by a team. As a result, there was no alteration in the research findings. All members of the research team agreed with the findings.

Findings

The participants of the study consisted of two females and two males. Most of the participants are married and specialized in hemodialysis, emergency room, operating room and medical-surgical ward. All nurses provided direct patient care except from one respondent who has been pulled-out from his respective areas.

Six themes were developed based on the responses of the participants, including fear of losing myself, anxiety is contagious, feeling betrayed by the government, being rejected, very supportive of our needs, and I miss my family. The respondents highlight these themes below:

Fear of Losing Myself

Most of their responses are fear of death, as no one will take care of their family because most of them are breadwinners. This is described in the following statements:

1. At first, I was totally scared because I felt as though I was going to die from COVID-19. I cried and I called my Mom and I told them to please quarantine yourself because I am positive.
2. I am scared and anxious because I saw a lot of patients who were intubated and that's the first thing that came to my mind when I watched the news.
3. I thought about my daughter; no one will take care of her once I die.
4. I am depressed and afraid to die early, and I think if I die early I have a lot of dreams for family. I was scared and stressed because I wasn't sure if I can make it. Until now I am still nervous. But I give everything to the Lord.

Anxiety is Really Contagious

Most of their responses are based on what the patient with COVID-19 experienced and the anxiety is easily transmitted to them psychologically, emotionally and physically. And through direct contact knowing the real condition of the patient or they based it from pre-diagnosis which is not COVID-19. Their answers are as follows:

1. I developed severe anxiety during my first two days of COVID-19. I am battling without knowing the possible outcome of having COVID-19. I always think that I acquired this from my patients not only because their anxious because I am having the same condition they experienced.
2. Anxiety is somehow communicable it can easily be transferred from a person who is normal especially when having the same signs and symptoms we experienced.

3. I remembered the patient I handled she cried all throughout and I cried secretly and felt anxious as well because we handled this patient long time ago with different diagnosis.
4. At first, I was in denial that I have COVID-19. All I know is just tonsillitis though I feel anxious, until the results came out and I am in active and confirmed COVID-19 positive together with my Dad and *Kuya* (elder brother).

Feeling Betrayed by the Government

Most of the participants said they are more likely betrayed by the Government that if they died their family will receive one million pesos and if they survived, they would pay the cost of admission, without knowing what they will get after this. It is determined in the following statements:

1. As we watched CNN as mentioned by the DOH spokesperson that If the health workers died with COVID-19 the family will receive one million, until I diagnosed with COVID-19, I looked on the brighter side that what if I died with this condition I hope my family will be happy with one million. Suddenly, I watched different news that one of our nurses from Taguig passed away from COVID-19, her family only received 7,000 pesos how sad that our worth as a front liner is only 7,000, not 1,000,000. Healthcare workers feel betrayed on this.
2. At first we didn't have enough PPE, mask and anything we just repeatedly used our resources, until the government says on National TV that we can reuse our mask by putting a gasoline on it. I feel saddened, maybe because that the government has no concrete plan for this.
3. What I felt is I am all alone in this battle. I am waiting for the vaccination the government has no clear statement on this.
4. I am hopeless if we were going to survive this pandemic our government can feel that the people are hopeless and the people felt they are betrayed by the government, exposing us to different patient without knowing our enemies. No concrete plan for the people.

Being Rejected

The majority of the participants agreed that they feel rejected before and after having COVID-19. Their neighborhood, friends, colleagues, and community despise them and are scared to speak with them for fear of becoming infected. The participants described this:

1. I feel all alone and my family, even though I am admitted in the hospital my family at home received a lot of rejection from our neighborhood and says "*Wag kayo lalabas diyan! Makakahawa pa kayo sa amin, maaawa naman kayo* (Don't go out there! You can still infect us, have pity on us)". My family knows the protocol even I am recovered they keep on gossiping me and says "*Kahit magaling ka na nakakahawa ka pa rin umalis na lang kayo dito sa lugar namin* (Even if you feel good and you are still contagious, just leave our place)".
2. When the time I tested positive our neighbor splashed a chlorine substance in front of our house and yelling, "*COVID umalis kayo sa lugar namin, salot kayo* (COVID, you better leave our place, you pest)". My Dad and my *Kuya* (elder brother) that our neighbor feels that they are pertaining to them.

I am home quarantined inside my room, so no one from my family is exposed because me and my Yaya are together but to make sure that my Yaya is negative I called the local government unit (LGU) for her to get tested and I am happy because she's negative. So I asked my Yaya through the intercom to buy fruits for me. The fruit vendor is rude to her and says, "*Ba't nasa labas ka? Di ba may COVID amo mo? Baka ikaw meron din. Maawa ka naman, naghahanapbuhay lang ako* (Why are you outside? Doesn't your boss have a COVID? Maybe you have too. Have mercy, I'm just making a living)". My Yaya told him that she is negative, and the vendor continue saying "*Sa susunod ka na lang bumili pag napakita muna resulta mo* (Just buy from us next time only when your results are shown)."

4. My neighbors stand in front of our house and making gossip to us most of the time until I recovered, and they kept gossiping about me and my family.

Very Supportive of our Needs

The institution is very supportive with our needs from free RT-PCR up to admission and discharge. Nurses said that they have nothing against their hospital because they provide what the healthcare workers want, and they felt like a family in this institution. As described in the statements:

1. This hospital provided everything we need from admission to discharge.
2. They made sure our family will not think of anything. They are very concerned with our health.
3. The test is always free and the food courtesy.
4. Very supportive to all front liners in the hospital

I miss my Family

Most of our nurses were admitted in the hospital but the others were in home quarantined. They usually return home as a precautionary measure to prevent the illness from spreading. As a result, they miss their home and loved ones. This is identified in the following statements:

1. It has been six months since I left our house in Dasmariñas, until I tested positive and recovered. I miss my family, our house and my dogs.
2. When the time I was admitted with COVID-19 until I recovered, I cried because if you are exposed to suspected COVID-19 automatically you are 14 days quarantine.
3. If you are on duty especially in COVID ward you are required to have at least 14 days quarantine and RT-PCR swab and I decided not to go home stay in dormitory of the hospital. Rather than expose my family.

Discussion

Six themes were developed and are as follows:

1. The first theme is **Fear of Losing Myself** indicated that no one wants to lose a fight where they could not see their enemies in the battle. This initial theme is the process of acceptance of nurses in taking care of patient infected with the virus.

This continues until they become desensitized over time and accept the situation that there are front liners who choose to save lives and fight against COVID19. This process can be deemed natural if the stages of change are recognized, allowing for a smooth transition from comfort to acceptance of the new normal. In addition, Gunawan et al. (2021) said that some nurses are even proud of their participation in the pandemic and becoming a part of history. These nurses, on the other hand, are likely to have strong coping mechanisms, such as faith in a higher power or surrendering to God with the notion that life or death is in God's hands. Surrender does not imply weakness; rather, it implies that effort and prayer have been combined. Moreover, according to the Philippine Nurses Association, approximately, 90 nurses in the Philippines lost their lives and died in the battle (De Castro et al., 2020). Nurses have seen many nurses die in saving others' lives in this pandemic.

2. The second theme is **Anxiety is Really Contagious**. Anxiety can easily be acquired from one person who experiences it to another who did not live with anxiety. Most of the participants struggle with being diagnosed with COVID19. Having this condition they assumed it is the end of their lives. Every time they feel anxious, they think of their families, and they pray to uplift themselves. Most of them cried to accept the situation. Many nurses are still concerned about patients, the danger of infecting family members, and the financial impact of the pandemic (Pearce, 2021).
3. Third theme is **Feeling Betrayed by the Government**. Nurses believe that instead of being viewed as heroes, they are seen as weapons by the enemy. They may believe that it makes no difference whether the nurses live or die. In the top echelons of government and hospitals, there is no one who cares or advocates for nurses. Nurses believe they are unable to speak up about their marginalization or to fight back for fear of losing their jobs and being fired by their employers (Gunawan et al., 2021).
4. **Being Rejected** is the fourth theme in which our current condition, which nurses have got as a result of their efforts to save people's lives. Nurses are frequently seen as both a virus recipient and a source of viral transmission (Gunawan et al., 2021), and they ignored by their peers and community. This produced a dreadful situation for front-line nurses who contracted the virus, and it was frequently the worst circumstance the nurses had ever encountered. Their sentiments of rejection and solitude contribute to their poor mental health. As a result, many nurses are now showing signs and symptoms of depression, stress, and other mental health problems (Gunawan et al., 2020). This rejection arises as a result of misinformation that society may be unable to verify.
5. The fifth theme is the institution is **Very Supportive of Our Needs**. Nurses are very lucky to be part of the institution where they are part of because the institution is very supportive to the needs of nurses. Investigating the challenges that nurses confront during their combat will aid in their assistance as well as the development of guidelines and plans to increase their preparedness. An integrative review will explore the issues being faced by nurses who are also patients of COVID-19.

The critical lack of nurses, beds, and medical supplies, including personal protective equipment, are among the key challenges confronting nurses in this situation, as do psychological changes and worries of infection; regardless of these issues, the important the institution must always be supportive to nurses and other health workers. These findings may aid in providing assistance and identifying the requirements of nurses in all affected regions of the hospital, allowing them to work and respond to the crisis with greater confidence. Furthermore, this will aid in improving pandemic preparedness and incorporating issues into crisis plans. The nurses should be supported since they are the first line of defense. In the field of pandemics, further study in the field of nursing is required (Dewart et al., 2020).

6. The last theme is in this study is **I miss my Family**; nurses miss their family a lot after being diagnosed as positive. They are devastated because they need to take care of themselves. Until now they miss their homes after being quarantined once exposed to a COVID-19 patient. The quarantine is in place to protect family members from local transmission. One nurse stated that she was unable to return home since she lives with two elderly parents and two teenage daughters (Marsiela, 2020). Nurses are isolated from their families for long periods of time because transmission is possible, and this sacrifice should be recognized. Nurses are today's actual heroes.

Conclusion

This study explored the lived experience of nurses as patients during COVID-19 pandemic and how to they transverse the caring encounters as Nurses. The results delivered the holistic approach in describing the nurse's feeling and current state of phenomena in the hospital as patient of COVID-19 and being quarantined at home. The emotions of nurses are mixed: pessimistic and optimistic behavior based on what they have experienced as a patient. However, most developed themes are considered negative, which is related to fear of losing myself, anxiety is contagious, feeling betrayed by the government, and being rejected. These results are reflections of what we are experiencing, and we need to help our nurses to be motivated amidst this pandemic. We should appreciate the modern-day heroes, which are the health workers (nurses, medical technologist, radiologic technologist, pharmacist, physical therapist and lastly our doctors) instead of labeling them as the source of viral infection. We must support our front liners all over the world who keep their smiles no matter the condition. Nightingale (2018) stated that on a daily basis, nurses empower and assist the patient to be in the best possible environment for nature to act.

References

- De Castro, L., Lopez, A. A., Hamoy, G., Alba, K. C., & Gundayao, J. C. (2020). A fair allocation approach to the ethics of scarce resources in the context of a pandemic: The need to prioritize the worst-off in the Philippines. *Developing World Bioethics*, 21(4), 153-172. <https://doi.org/10.1111/dewb.12293>
- Department of Health. (2021, April 17). *DOH COVID-19 bulletin # 399*. <https://doh.gov.ph/covid19casebulletin399>
- Dewart, G., Corcoran, L., Thirsk, L., & Petrovic, K. (2020). Nursing education in a pandemic: Academic challenges in response to COVID-19. *Nurse Education Today*, 92, 104471. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nedt.2020.104471>
- Djalante, R., Nurhidayah, L., Van Minh, H., Phuong, N. T. N., Mahendradhata, Y., Trias, A., Lassa, J., & Miller, M. A. (2020). COVID-19 and ASEAN responses: Comparative policy analysis. *Progress in Disaster Science*, 8, 100129. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pdisas.2020.100129>
- Gunawan, J., Aunguroch, Y., Marzilli, C., Fisher, M. L., & Sukarna, A. (2021). A phenomenological study of the lived experience of nurses in the battle of COVID-19. *Nursing Outlook*, 69(4), 652-659. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.outlook.2021.01.020>
- Gunawan, J., Juthamane, S., & Aunguroch, Y. (2020). Current mental health issues in the era of Covid-19. *Asian Journal of Psychiatry*, 51, 102103. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ajp.2020.102103>
- International Council of Nurses. (2020, October 28). *ICN confirms 1,500 nurses have died from COVID-19 in 44 countries and estimates that healthcare worker COVID-19 fatalities worldwide could be more than 20,000*. <https://www.icn.ch/news/icn-confirms-1500-nurses-have-died-covid-19-44-countries-and-estimates-healthcare-worker-covid>
- International Council of Nurses. (2021, January 13). *International council of nurses COVID-19 update*. <https://www.icn.ch/sites/default/files/inline-files/ICN%20COVID19%20update%20report%20FINAL.pdf>
- Marsiela, A. (2020, March 9). *Referral hospitals in areas lacking PPE to handle corona cases*. *Berita Satu*. <https://www.beritasatu.com/nasional/606973/rumah-sakit-rujukan-di-daerah-kekurangan-apd-untuk-tangani-kasus-corona>
- Naguit, R. J. (2020). *Philippines: COVID-19 as a public health crisis*. Friedrich-Ebert-Stiftung. <https://asia.fes.de/news/philippines-covid-19-as-a-public-health-crisis>
- Nightingale, F. (2018). *Notes on nursing: Commemorative edition*. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- Pearce, S. (2021). *The time is now: Empowering nurses in electoral politics* (Doctoral dissertation, Yale University). ProQuest Dissertations Publishing. <https://www.proquest.com/openview/638e2fcb9ee3921d36656c9a18047e3f/1?pq-origsite=gscholar&cbl=18750&diss=y>
- Polit, D. F., & Beck, C.T. (2013). *Essentials of nursing research: Appraising evidence for nursing practice*. Lippincott Williams & Wilkins.
- World Health Organization. (2021, April 17). *Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) pandemic*. <https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019>
- Worldometers. (2020). *COVID-19 coronavirus pandemic*. <https://www.worldometers.info/coronavirus/>
- van Manen, M. (2014). *Phenomenology of practice: Meaning-giving methods in phenomenological research and writing*. Routledge.
- Visagie, N. (2020). Mitigating the psychological and mental health impact on frontline workers during COVID-19. *Belitung Nursing Journal*, 6(4), 141-142. <https://doi.org/10.33546/bnj.1171>